

The Green Software Engineering Challenge

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Achieving net zero will require a paradigm shift in our thinking, requiring everyone to participate, and the net zero ambition to be embedded in all organisational layers and across all research council activities. For Digital Research Infrastructure, an important part of that transformation will be Green Software Engineering.

Traditionally, Software Engineering has focussed on functionality, reliability, extensibility and how well the software product performs in terms of time, hardware resources and people to maintain it. The green software engineering (GSE) challenge is to limit carbon consumption at all stages of the software engineering lifecycle, from the gathering of requirements through the design, development, implementation and deployment of software. And to empower the users of software packages (including trained machine learning models, climate models etc.) to do so with the least environmental impact. Large reductions in DRI energy requirements could also be achieved simply by computing less and sharing existing results more effectively.

Diagram of the stages of the software engineering lifecycle

Source: <https://technogeekscs.com/software-developer-lifecycle/>

It is recommended to invest in Green Software Engineers. An initial GSE pool of talent would be a central UKRI team of people with relevant skills/experience to provide support and training in how to make both software greener and the use of software greener. These GSEs could help with selected codes, for example the software codes with high resource use identified in the HPC-JEEP report¹ which will give immediate carbon savings.

The GSEs would write these up as Case Studies and provide training, such that further people gain relevant skills who then support and train further people (and recursively until all

¹ Turner, Andrew, & Basden, Alastair. (2022). HPC-JEEP: Energy Usage on ARCHER2 and the DiRAC COSMA HPC services (v1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7137390>

researchers, and users/managers of facilities have acquired such knowledge). The pool of GSEs would grow over time and members would be available to UKRI researchers and facility managers.

Useful resources

Green Coding <https://www.green-coding.io/>

Green Software Foundation <https://greensoftware.foundation/>

Green Compute UK <http://greencompute.uk>

Green Algorithms <https://www.green-algorithms.org/>

Supporting Recommendations

The UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project's final technical report: Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure², contains many recommendations about the role of green software engineering skills and practices in the journey to net zero DRI.

A general discussion of the recommendations can be found in section 3.2 of the [Net Zero DRI final report](#). A full list of the recommendations can be found in Appendix 3 of the final report and in addition can be accessed via this [spreadsheet](#).

Providing & running a data centre

Recommendations 32, 33, 51, 60, 72: Cap and Share/ Green Scheduler/ Grid aware computing
Recommendations 34, 77, 81: Taking steps to reduce idling power and default frequency of CPUs and GPUs (whilst being aware that in some cases, lower frequency may result in higher energy to solution).

Recommendations 82, 135: Maximise the use of embodied emissions through high utilisation of resources.

Recommendation 15: Extending the lifetime (and re-use) of servers.

Recommendation 35: Buying the most appropriate hardware.

Roadmap Action 17: Integrate sustainable computing within DRI career development pathways.

Designing and writing carbon aware/efficient scientific software

Recommendation 136: Optimising code and reducing coding mistakes.

Recommendation 137: Principles of green software design: code review, testing, workflows, compilation optimised for energy efficiency, experiment design.

Using “black box” software more sustainably

Recommendation 140: Invest in research and development of better tools. ... improve energy efficiency of scientific software. ... energy efficiency of software products usable by non-expert researchers.

² Juckes, M., Bane, M., Bulpett, J., Cartmell, K., MacFarlane, M., MacRae, M., Owen, A., Pascoe, C., & Townsend, P. (2023). Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure: UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project final technical report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199984>

Training

Final Report Section 2.1.6: Skillset of the pool of Green Software Engineers

Recommendation 45: Develop RSE skill base. Training for RSEs to develop efficient code.

Recommendation 86: Training for users on energy efficiency and carbon emissions.

Recommendation 130: Provide training to PhD students and early career researchers to work with specialised low carbon data storage and computing facilities.

Recommendation 139: Ensure adequate training of experts. Ensure adequate training specifically code review, GSE practices, code energy efficiency evaluation and optimisation, compilation optimisation for energy efficiency, design of experiments.

Recommendation 147: Train RSEs to provide cross-sector support to optimise code for deployment (re: carbon efficiency). ... dedicated teams of Research Software Engineers (RSEs).

Open Science

Roadmap Action 15: Adopt standards for Open Science principles and apply across the DRI.

Recommendation 18: Adopt standards for open research practice using DRI. Open Science enables greater efficiency in scientific workflows.

Recommendation 31: Ensure researchers follow best practice in the sustainable use of DRI whilst recognising the need to advance knowledge, e.g., by reusing DRI, data and code where possible, ensuring new code is optimised, embedding FAIR data practices, and considering whether the proposed research or new DRI is really required.